

**IDENTITY POLITICS OF DR. B. R. AMBEDKAR: WAS HE A TRUE
NATIONALIST OR ANTI-NATIONALIST LEADER**

Narayana

Research Scholar, Dept. of Political Science, Bangalore University Bengaluru-560056

Email: nschawan28@gmail.com

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The Bharatiya concept of Rashtra could be considered a parallel to the Western term ‘Nation’ but both are also different on several counts. The primary difference between the two stems from the fact that ‘Rashtra’ is more of an ethic-spiritual concept while the nation is a cultural concept. Many Indian leaders like Sri Arvindo, Mahatma Gandhi, Nehru, Tilak, Tagore, and Deen Dayal Upadhyay delved into the idea of the Indian nation and nationalism. Their ideas are either spiritual, metaphysical, or statist. On the other side, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar elaborated on the idea of Nationality and Nationalism in his book Pakistan or the Partition of India. He describes nationality as a “consciousness of kind, awareness of the existence of that tie of kinship and nationalism as the desire for a separate national existence for those who are bound by this tie of kinship”.

Dr. Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar (14 April 1891 – 6 December 1956), popularly also recognized as Babasaheb, was an Indian jurist, political leader, philosopher, anthropologist, historian, orator, economist, teacher, editor, prolific writer, revolutionary, and a revivalist for Buddhism in India. He was also the chief architect of the Indian Constitution. Born into a poor Mahar (measured as an Untouchable caste) family, Ambedkar campaigned against social discrimination, the system of Chaturvarna – the categorization of Hindu civilization into four varnas – and the Hindu caste system. He converted to Buddhism and is also credited with providing a spark for transforming hundreds of thousands of Dalits or untouchables to Theravada Buddhism. Ambedkar was posthumously awarded the Bharat Ratna, India's highest civilian award, in 1990. Overcoming numerous social and financial obstacles, Ambedkar became one of the first Dalits (untouchables) to obtain a college education in India. Eventually earning a law degree and doctorate for his revise and research in law,

economics, and political science from Columbia University and the London School of Economics, Ambedkar gained a reputation as a scholar and practiced law for a few years, later campaigning by publishing journals advocating political rights and social freedom for India's untouchables. Ambedkar is the tallest leader of Dalits in India. Ambedkar belonged to the community of untouchables in Maharashtra. Hence he had first-hand experience of what it means to be untouchable in India. No other Dalit leader could achieve what Ambedkar could achieve for his community (Dhananjaya Keer – writer of the biography of Ambedkar). Ambedkar is also a controversial personality like Sir Sayed Ahmed Khan.

Ambedkar was fortunate enough to get an opportunity to gain a western education. He earned a law degree and started practicing law in Mumbai. However, because of his caste, nobody approached Ambedkar for his services. Hence Ambedkar realized that even when Dalits are educated, they will not be able to live a life of dignity. Hence he believed that untouchability has to be abolished to address the exploitation of Dalits. He dedicated himself to the cause of the abolition of untouchability by raising awareness amongst Dalits. He brought the magazine 'Mukanayak' (January 1920) and he brought the newspaper 'Bahishkrit Bharat' (April 1927). He established Bahishkrit Hitkarni Sabha (1924), Janata (1930), Prabuddha Bharat (1956) the All India Depressed Classes Federation (1928) which was renamed the Republican Party of India (1956). Ambedkar also adopted the Gandhian technique of Satyagraha. He organized Mahad satyagraha, he asserted the rights of untouchables to take water from the same well, which is used by 'caste Hindus'. Ambedkar was disappointed as he could not get the support of Gandhi for his satyagraha. Gandhi held that for the time being satyagraha should be used only against colonial authorities. Ultimately Ambedkar felt that untouchables should take the help of the British state in improving their status. Ambedkar never believed in the commitment of Gandhi towards the upliftment of untouchables. One of the grievances of Ambedkar against Gandhi has been that Gandhi never kept any fast for the abolition of untouchability.

Ideological Orientation

He thought that liberalism upheld a narrow conception of freedom which tolerated huge accumulation of resources in a few hands and the deprivation and exploitation it bred. He argued that liberal systems conceal deep inequalities of minorities such as the conditions of the Blacks in the U.S.A. and Jews in Europe. Liberal stress on the individual and ignored community bonds and the necessity of the latter to sustain a reflective and creative self. He felt that the principle of equality before the law is truly a great advance as compared to the

egalitarian orders that it attempted to supplant but it is not adequate. He argued that a good society demands extensive public ownership of the means of production and equal opportunity for everyone to develop his or herself to the fullest extent. He further argued that a desirable political order can be created only by acknowledging a moral domain which he saw eminently expressed in the Buddha's teachings. Ambedkar felt that rights and humanity cannot be left to the mercy and prejudices of people who have developed a vested interest in undermining them.

Ambedkar as an anti-nationalist?

Arun Shourie in his book, "Worshipping False God" has called Ambedkar 'anti-national'. He has given the following reasons.

1. Ambedkar opposed the Purna Swaraj resolution of 1929. During the first session of the All-India Depressed Classes Congress (AIDCC), on August 8, 1930, at Nagpur, he opposed the project of India's independence, which the Congress had promoted a few months before, in December 1929, during its Karachi session, under pressure from Jawaharlal Nehru. The AIDCC argued that "the depressed classes welcomed the British as their deliverers from age-long tyranny and oppression by the orthodox Hindus". Ambedkar felt strengthened in these views after Congress won the 1937 elections started to rule eight out of 11 provinces, and passed conservative bills, including the Industrial Dispute Bill that made strikes illegal under certain conditions in the Bombay presidency. In 1939, Ambedkar made his stand clear in the legislative council of this province: "Whenever there is any conflict of interest between the country and the untouchables, so far as I am concerned, the untouchables' interests will take precedence over the interests will take precedence over the interests of the country". On 8th Aug 1930, Ambedkar held that depressed classes should be grateful to the British for improving their status.

Ambedkar directed Dalits to stay away from a) Gandhi's Harijana Sevak Sanghs and b) To stay away from Indian National Congress.

4. Ambedkar called the Poona Pact a Himalayan blunder; he wanted separate electorates for Dalits. The Poona Pact was signed at 5 pm on September 24 by 23 people. Madan Mohan Malaviya signed it on behalf of Hindus Gandhi, and Ambedkar on behalf of the depressed classes. Instead of the 80 seats given by the British, the depressed, the depressed classes got 148 seats. At the end of the talks, Gandhi's trusted emissary, C. Rajagopalachari, exchanged his fountain pen with Ambedkar. What did Congress and Gandhi have done to the

Untouchables? “if you devoted yourself entirely to the welfare of the depressed classes, then you would become our hero”, Ambedkar told Gandhi during the negotiations.

5. Ambedkar criticized the ‘Quit India Movement’ as the ‘Mad-venture of Gandhi’. During WW 2nd, he decided to cooperate with the British for another reason. Like Nehru, he thought that the Italian Fascists and Japan were more dangerous than the British. Opposing Mahatma Gandhi’s decision, in August 1942, to launch the Quit India Movement, he declared that the “patriotic duty of all Indians” was rather to prevent such movements from creating “anarchy and chaos which would unquestionably help and facilitate the subjugation of this country by japan”.

6. Ambedkar supported Jinnah’s demand for Pakistan. In March, the All India Muslim League passed the Lahore resolution for the creation of ‘Independent States’ from the predominantly Muslim areas of India, once the British ended their rule. Immediately after the resolution was passed, the executive council of the Independent Labour Party (ILP)- formed in 1936 under Dr. Ambedkar’s leadership met to consider their stance on the ‘project of Pakistan’. The council appointed a committee to study the issue and produce a report, with Dr. Ambedkar as its chairperson. The Muslim League demanded that “Punjab, the North-Western Frontier Province, Baluchistan, and Sind in the North-West and Bengal in the East instead of remaining as the provinces of British India shall be incorporated as independent States outside of British India”. Dr. Ambedkar States that “The League has only enlarged the original scheme of Pakistan. It has sought to create one more Muslim state in the east to include the Muslims in Bengal and Assam”. He says that Hinduism has not been a proselytizing religion since the caste system came to exist. He further states that Muhammad Ali Jinnah and V.D. Savarkar appear to be opposed to each other, but agree about the ‘one nation versus two nations issue’. Both insist that India has two nations, one Muslim and another Hindu. Dr. Ambedkar writes: “Mr. Jinnah says India should be cut up into two, Pakistan and Hindustan. Mr. Savarkar, on the other hand, insists that, although there are two nations in India, India shall not be divided into two parts, one for Muslims and the other for Hindus; that the two nations shall dwell in one country and shall live under the mantle of one single constitution; that the constitution shall be such that the Hindu nation will be enabled to occupy a predominant position that is due to it and the Muslim nation made to live in the position of subordinate co-operation with the Hindu-Nation”. “but far more distressing is the fact that there is no organized movement of social reform among the Musalmans of India on a scale sufficient to bring about their eradication”. The reason for this is that the social

environment is predominantly Hindi. The Muslim community's", separate polls for Muslims and non-Muslims should be conducted in predominantly Muslim provinces. Suppose most Muslims favor and most non-Muslims disfavor the separation. In that case, steps must be taken- and wherever possible, provincial boundaries shall be redrawn- to separate the Muslim majority districts from the others.

7. Ambedkar wanted the Britishers to stay. On the contrary, at every available opportunity, he was persuading the British to stay back in India and made every attempt possible to derail the freedom movement. For instance, it was Ambedkar's firm opinion that "if India became independent, it would be one of the greatest disasters that could happen".

8. Ambedkar joined the defense advisory committee formed by the British as well as the Viceroy's executive council which was set up to gain legitimacy for British efforts.

Thus on the above basis, certain sections of Indian political class and intellectuals call Ambedkar anti-nationalist. Like Sir Sayed Ahmed Khan, Ambedkar also emerged as the leader of the community rather than the leader of the Nation. Ambedkar himself held that between the interests of the Dalits and the interest of the nation, I will give preference to the interest of the Dalits.

Ambedkar as a True Nationalist

However, according to Arundhati Roy and Christophe Jaffrelot, it would be wrong to call Ambedkar anti-national for the following reasons:

- Ambedkar represented the largest section of Indian society (Bahujana samaj). A person representing the largest section of the nation cannot be regarded as anti-national. On the status of India as a Nation, Ambedkar's approach was as practical as that of Jyotiba Phule. It was difficult for Ambedkar to accept a society divided into castes as a nation. The concept of Nation, according to Ambedkar is based on the trinity of liberty, fraternity, and equality. There can be no nation without this trinity. However, it does not mean that there was no desire in Ambedkar that India should not emerge as a nation. In his speech to the constituent assembly in Dec 1946, he held that 'I know, we are divided politically, economically and socially. We are a group of warring camps; I am a leader of one such camp.' However, I am convinced that a day will come when we will forget these differences and emerge as a nation.
- Ambedkar believed that the sooner we accept that we are not a Nation, the better it is, at least we will start thinking about how to become a nation by understanding why we are not a nation. He did not think that India was a nation: "How can people divided into several thousands of castes be a nation?" he asked. For him, the national movement was dominated

by an elite, of which the masses were the first victims. For, as he said in 1943 before trade union activists, the working classes often sacrificed their all to the so-called cause of nationalism. They have never cared to enquire whether the nationalism for which they are to make their offerings will when established, give them social and economic equality”.

Some of his speeches and writings express how B. R. Ambedkar was a true nationalist far as the ultimate goal is concerned, none of us have any apprehension or doubt. Our difficulty was not about the ultimate thing but how to unite the heterogeneous mass that we are today to decide in common and march in a cooperative way on that road, which is bound to lead us to unity.

Dr. Ambedkar spoke in a felicitation program for his 50th birth anniversary, "I have loyalty to our people inhabiting this country. I do not doubt that you have the same. All of us want this country to be free. So far as I am concerned my conduct has been guided by the consideration that we shall place no great difficulties in the way of this country achieving its freedom". He talked about the freedom of India from social inequality and untouchability. Ambedkar was not against the idea of nationalism but against the Congress's version which entailed freedom of India from British colonialism but not from Brahminical imperialism under which millions of Scheduled Castes had been yoked for hundreds of years. Without social union, political unity is difficult to be achieved, if achieved, it would be as precarious as a summer sapling, liable to be uprooted by the gust of a hostile wind. With mere political unity, India may be a State. But to be a State is not to be a Nation and a State, which is not a Nation, has small prospects of survival in the struggle for existence”.

Great faith in Bharat- Dr. Ambedkar had great faith in ancient Indian institutions and texts except for caste. He has written about the Annihilation of Caste, not Dharma. He favored Indian Dharma (Religion), India's Ancient democratic principles, parliamentary system, etc. he has the idea that Hindus need not borrow from foreign sources concepts to build a society on the principles of equality, fraternity, and liberty. They 'could draw from such principles in the Upanishads. Even in Riddles in Hinduism, he points out that Hinduism has the potential to become the spiritual basis of social democracy. For the removal and elimination of the Caste and Brahminical system, he believed strong Centre (strong Union) government in India. Ambedkar in his very first speech in the Constituent Assembly on 17 December 1946 emphasized the need to create a strong Centre to ensure that India's freedom was not jeopardized as had happened in the past on account of weak central administration. Further, he was opposed to giving special status to Jammu and Kashmir under

Article 370 as well as against giving autonomy to local government. because it would weak Unity of a strong State”.

Gandhi and Ambedkar

- Gandhi believed that if a person is born in a particular religion, there is a divine will. One can accept good things from other religions but one should not leave one's religion.
- On the other hand, Ambedkar wanted to convert. He even explored conversion in Islam and Christianity but ultimately found spiritual satisfaction in Buddhism.
- Ambedkar and Gandhi also had a debate over the Varna system. Gandhi believed the Varna system was a division of labor. It is a feature of even advanced societies. However, Gandhi rejected the caste system. Gandhi was also against untouchability.
- Ambedkar held that Gandhi's description is too idealistic, and textual. Varna is a text, caste in context. In reality, Varna exists as a caste.
- Caste is not the division of labor, it is a division of laborers. It is also not a sensible economic system. Profession is not based on merit but based on birth.
- Gandhi's impracticality is evident as Gandhi himself was not observing his Varna dharma. Hence abolition of caste and Varna is the same.
- Ambedkar criticized Harijana Sevak Sangh formed by Gandhi. He compared Harijana Sevak Sangh with Putna(the mythological character sent to kill Krishna by nursing poison in the form of milk)
- Ambedkar had objections concerning the use of the word Harijana. According to Ambedkar, it is a misleading term because it does not tell the real status of untouchables in Indian society. It may push them into 'false consciousness'.
- Hence Ambedkar preferred to use the term dalits and depressed classes. If Gandhi was the father of the nation, Ambedkar was the constitution's father. The two leaders had similar aims though their paths were different. Arundhati Roy addresses Gandhi as a saint and Ambedkar as a Doctor.

Relevance of Ambedkar at the present times

Caste-based inequality in India persists. While Dalits have acquired a political identity through reservation and forming their political parties, they are behind in social dimensions (health and education) and economic dimensions. Dr. Ambedkar did give us a grand-narrative of 'equality in socio-economic life along with political equality'.

There has been a rise in communal polarization and communalization of politics. Ambedkar's vision of constitutional morality must supersede religious morality to avoid permanent damage to the Indian Constitution.

Justice K. Ramaswamy calls Ambedkar a true democrat, a nationalist to the core, and a patriot of the highest order on various grounds.

Dr. Krishna Gopal (Joint General Secretary, RSS) claimed, 'Besides being a champion of the untouchables, Ambedkar was, first and foremost, a nationalist, a virulent anti-communist and had immense faith in Hinduism'

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